

Raport statystyczny

Demographic characteristics of the studied groups.

Age

```
statystyki_wiek_all <- dane %>%
  summarise(
    Średnia = mean(age, na.rm = TRUE),
    SD      = sd(age, na.rm = TRUE),
    Mediana = median(age, na.rm = TRUE),
    Min     = min(age, na.rm = TRUE),
    Max     = max(age, na.rm = TRUE),
    Ilość   = sum(!is.na(age))
  ) %>%
  mutate(Zmienna = "age") %>%
  select(Zmienna, everything())

library(flextable)
statystyki_wiek_all_flextable <- statystyki_wiek_all %>%
  flextable() %>%
  colformat_double(j = c("Średnia", "SD", "Mediana", "Min", "Max"), digits = 2)
%>%
  set_caption("Age - overall") %>%
  theme_vanilla() %>%
  autofit()

statystyki_wiek_all_flextable
```

Zmienna	Średnia	SD	Mediana	Min	Max	Ilość	
age	66.97	7.00	68.50	52.00	78.00	40	
group	Średnia	SD	Mediana	Min	Max	Ilość	Zmienna
HTG	69.00	6.80	70.00	54.00	78.00	10	age
K	67.80	6.11	68.00	58.00	78.00	15	age
NTG	64.80	7.80	67.00	52.00	78.00	15	age

Normality in groups for age

Shapiro-Wilk test for age (grupa 'NTG')

- Statystyka W = 0.951
- p-value = 0.5462

Shapiro-Wilk test for age (grupa 'HTG')

- Statystyka W = 0.922

- p-value = 0.3749

Shapiro-Wilk test for age (grupa 'Control')

- Statystyka W = 0.955
- p-value = 0.5997

Homogeneity of variance

Levene's test for age

- Statystyka F = 0.875
- p-value = 0.4251

ANOVA for age

ANOVA for age (age ~ group)

- Statystyka F = 1.262
- Stopnie swobody: grupa = 2, resztkowe = 37
- p-value = 0.295

Means for groups:

- HTG: 69 - K: 67.8 - NTG: 64.8

Gender

```
tab <- dane %>%
  mutate(
    sex = ifelse(sex %in% c(0, "k"), "Female", "Male")
  ) %>%
  filter(!is.na(group)) %>%
  count(group, sex, name = "n") %>%

  complete(group, sex = c("Female","Male"), fill = list(n = 0)) %>%
  group_by(group) %>%
  mutate(
    N = sum(n),
    pct = round(100 * n / N),
    cell = sprintf("%d (%d%)", n, pct)
  ) %>%
  select(group, sex, cell, N) %>%
  pivot_wider(
    names_from = sex,
    values_from = cell,
    names_glue = "{sex} n (%)",
    values_fill = list(cell = "0 (0%)")
  ) %>%
```

```

mutate(All = N) %>%
select(group, `Female n (%)`, `Male n (%)`, All) %>%
arrange(group) %>%
ungroup()

tab

# A tibble: 3 × 4
  group `Female n (%)` `Male n (%)`   All
  <fct> <chr>         <chr>         <int>
1 HTG   6 (60%)          4 (40%)          10
2 K     12 (80%)         3 (20%)          15
3 NTG  14 (93%)         1 (7%)           15

tab3x2 <- with(dane, table(group, ifelse(sex %in% c(0,"k"), "Female",
"Male")))
tab3x2

group Female Male
HTG      6     4
K       12     3
NTG     14     1

fisher.test(tab3x2)

      Fisher's Exact Test for Count Data

data:  tab3x2
p-value = 0.1476
alternative hypothesis: two.sided

```

Sex distribution did not differ across groups (Fisher's exact test, 3×2), p = 0.148.

Clinical characteristics of the studied groups

MD

```

dane <- dane %>%
  mutate(
    `MD.OP` = as.numeric(gsub(",", ".", as.character(`MD.OP`))),
    `MD.OL` = as.numeric(gsub(",", ".", as.character(`MD.OL`)))
  )

dane_noK <- dane %>%
  filter(group %in% c("NTG","HTG")) %>%
  mutate(group = factor(group, levels = c("NTG","HTG")))

statystyki_md_noK <- dane_noK %>%
  select(group, `MD.OP`, `MD.OL`) %>%

```

```

pivot_longer(cols = c(`MD.OP`, `MD.OL`),
             names_to = "Zmienna", values_to = "MD") %>%
group_by(group, Zmienna) %>%
summarise(
  Średnia = mean(MD, na.rm = TRUE),
  SD      = sd(MD, na.rm = TRUE),
  Mediana = median(MD, na.rm = TRUE),
  Min     = min(MD, na.rm = TRUE),
  Max     = max(MD, na.rm = TRUE),
  Ilość  = sum(!is.na(MD)),
  .groups = "drop"
) %>%
arrange(Zmienna, group)

gt(statystyki_md_noK, rowname_col = "group", groupname_col = "Zmienna") %>%
cols_label(
  group = "Grupa",
  Średnia = "Mean",
  SD     = "SD",
  Mediana = "Median",
  Min    = "Min",
  Max    = "Max",
  Ilość  = "N"
) %>%
fmt_number(columns = c(Średnia, SD, Mediana, Min, Max), decimals = 2) %>%
tab_header(title = md("**MD.OP i MD.OL vs NTG and HTG**")) %>%
tab_style(style = cell_text(weight = "bold"), locations =
cells_row_groups()) %>%
opt_row_stripping() %>%
tab_options(table.font.size = px(14))

```

Table 1: MD.OP i MD.OL vs NTG and HTG

	Mean	SD	Median	Min	Max	N
MD.OL						
NTG	-3.71	2.07	-3.61	-6.97	-0.27	15
HTG	-3.04	1.44	-3.21	-5.24	-0.63	10
MD.OP						
NTG	-3.18	2.18	-3.01	-6.79	-0.17	15
HTG	-2.83	1.76	-1.81	-5.36	-0.51	10

```

dane <- dane %>%
mutate(
  `MD.OP` = as.numeric(gsub(",", ".", as.character(`MD.OP`))),
  `MD.OL` = as.numeric(gsub(",", ".", as.character(`MD.OL`)))
)

dane_noK <- dane %>%
filter(group %in% c("NTG", "HTG"))

```

```

statystyki_md_all <- dane_noK %>%
  select(`MD.OP`, `MD.OL`) %>%
  pivot_longer(c(`MD.OP`, `MD.OL`),
               names_to = "Zmienna", values_to = "MD") %>%
  group_by(Zmienna) %>%
  summarise(
    Średnia = mean(MD, na.rm = TRUE),
    SD      = sd(MD, na.rm = TRUE),
    Mediana = median(MD, na.rm = TRUE),
    Min     = min(MD, na.rm = TRUE),
    Max     = max(MD, na.rm = TRUE),
    Ilość   = sum(!is.na(MD)),
    .groups = "drop"
  ) %>%
  mutate(group = "NTG+HTG") %>%
  select(group, everything())

# 4) Tabela gt (identyczne formatowanie jak wcześniej)
gt(statystyki_md_all, rowname_col = "group", groupname_col = "Zmienna") %>%
  cols_label(
    group      = "Grupa",
    Średnia    = "Mean",
    SD         = "SD",
    Mediana    = "Median",
    Min        = "Min",
    Max        = "Max",
    Ilość      = "N"
  ) %>%
  fmt_number(columns = c(Średnia, SD, Mediana, Min, Max), decimals = 2) %>%
  tab_header(title = md("**MD.OP i MD.OL – łącznie dla NTG+HTG**")) %>%
  tab_style(style = cell_text(weight = "bold"), locations =
cells_row_groups()) %>%
  opt_row_stripping() %>%
  tab_options(table.font.size = px(14))

```

Table 2: MD.OP i MD.OL – łącznie dla NTG+HTG

	Mean	SD	Median	Min	Max	N
MD.OL						
NTG+HTG	-3.44	1.84	-3.54	-6.97	-0.27	25
MD.OP						
NTG+HTG	-3.04	1.99	-2.86	-6.79	-0.17	25

MD OP

Shapiro-Wilk test for MD OP(grupa 'HTG')

- Statystyka W = 0.844
- p-value = 0.04923

Shapiro-Wilk test for MD OP(grupa 'NTG')

- Statystyka W = 0.931
- p-value = 0.2857

```
dane_noK <- dane %>%
  filter(group %in% c("NTG","HTG")) %>%
  mutate(
    group = factor(group, levels = c("NTG","HTG")),
    `MD.OP` = as.numeric(gsub(",", ".", as.character(`MD.OP`)))
  )

t_welch <- t.test(`MD.OP` ~ group, data = dane_noK, var.equal = FALSE)
t_welch
```

Welch Two Sample t-test

```
data: MD.OP by group
t = -0.4505, df = 22.053, p-value = 0.6568
alternative hypothesis: true difference in means between group NTG and group
HTG is not equal to 0
95 percent confidence interval:
 -1.996495  1.283828
sample estimates:
mean in group NTG mean in group HTG
   -3.183333      -2.827000
```

MD OL

Shapiro-Wilk test for MD OL(grupa 'HTG')

- Statystyka W = 0.948
- p-value = 0.6403

Shapiro-Wilk test for MD OL(grupa 'NTG')

- Statystyka W = 0.95
- p-value = 0.5169

```
dane_noK <- dane %>%
  filter(group %in% c("NTG","HTG")) %>%
  mutate(
    group = factor(group, levels = c("NTG","HTG")),
    `MD.OL` = as.numeric(gsub(",", ".", as.character(`MD.OL`)))
  )

# Welch's t-test (domyślnie two.sided; var.equal=FALSE -> brak założenia
równych wariancji)
t_welch <- t.test(`MD.OL` ~ group, data = dane_noK, var.equal = FALSE)
t_welch
```

Welch Two Sample t-test

```
data: MD.OL by group
t = -0.95694, df = 22.907, p-value = 0.3486
alternative hypothesis: true difference in means between group NTG and group
HTG is not equal to 0
95 percent confidence interval:
 -2.1271319  0.7817986
sample estimates:
mean in group NTG mean in group HTG
    -3.710667      -3.038000
```

VFI

```
dane <- dane %>%
  mutate(
    `VFI.OP` = as.numeric(gsub(",", ".", as.character(`VFI.OP`))),
    `VFI.OL` = as.numeric(gsub(",", ".", as.character(`VFI.OL`)))
  )

dane_noK <- dane %>%
  filter(group %in% c("NTG", "HTG")) %>%
  mutate(group = factor(group, levels = c("NTG", "HTG")))

statystyki_vfi_noK <- dane_noK %>%
  select(group, `VFI.OP`, `VFI.OL`) %>%
  pivot_longer(cols = c(`VFI.OP`, `VFI.OL`),
               names_to = "Zmienna", values_to = "VFI") %>%
  group_by(group, Zmienna) %>%
  summarise(
    Średnia = mean(VFI, na.rm = TRUE),
    SD      = sd(VFI, na.rm = TRUE),
    Mediana = median(VFI, na.rm = TRUE),
    Min     = min(VFI, na.rm = TRUE),
    Max     = max(VFI, na.rm = TRUE),
    Ilość   = sum(!is.na(VFI)),
    .groups = "drop"
  ) %>%
  arrange(Zmienna, group)

gt(statystyki_vfi_noK, rowname_col = "group", groupname_col = "Zmienna") %>%
  cols_label(
    group = "Grupa",
    Średnia = "Mean",
    SD      = "SD",
    Mediana = "Median",
    Min     = "Min",
    Max     = "Max",
```

```

    Ilość = "N"
  ) %>%
  fmt_number(columns = c(Średnia, SD, Mediana, Min, Max), decimals = 2) %>%
  tab_header(title = md("***VFI.OP i VFI.OL vs NTG and HTG**")) %>%
  tab_style(style = cell_text(weight = "bold"), locations =
cells_row_groups()) %>%
  opt_row_stripping() %>%
  tab_options(table.font.size = px(14))

```

Table 3: VFI.OP i VFI.OL vs NTG and HTG

	Mean	SD	Median	Min	Max	N
VFI.OL						
NTG	88.40	8.64	91.00	74.00	99.00	15
HTG	94.30	3.13	95.50	89.00	98.00	10
VFI.OP						
NTG	88.67	7.03	86.00	76.00	98.00	15
HTG	94.60	3.81	97.00	88.00	98.00	10

```

dane <- dane %>%
  mutate(
    `VFI.OP` = as.numeric(gsub(",", ".", as.character(`VFI.OP`))),
    `VFI.OL` = as.numeric(gsub(",", ".", as.character(`VFI.OL`)))
  )

dane_noK <- dane %>%
  filter(group %in% c("NTG", "HTG"))

statystyki_vfi_all <- dane_noK %>%
  select(`VFI.OP`, `VFI.OL`) %>%
  pivot_longer(c(`VFI.OP`, `VFI.OL`),
    names_to = "Zmienna", values_to = "VFI") %>%
  group_by(Zmienna) %>%
  summarise(
    Średnia = mean(VFI, na.rm = TRUE),
    SD = sd(VFI, na.rm = TRUE),
    Mediana = median(VFI, na.rm = TRUE),
    Min = min(VFI, na.rm = TRUE),
    Max = max(VFI, na.rm = TRUE),
    Ilość = sum(!is.na(VFI)),
    .groups = "drop"
  ) %>%
  mutate(group = "NTG+HTG") %>%
  select(group, everything())

gt(statystyki_vfi_all, rowname_col = "group", groupname_col = "Zmienna") %>%
  cols_label(
    group = "Grupa",

```

```

Średnia = "Mean",
SD       = "SD",
Mediana = "Median",
Min      = "Min",
Max      = "Max",
Ilość   = "N"
) %>%
fmt_number(columns = c(Średnia, SD, Mediana, Min, Max), decimals = 2) %>%
tab_header(title = md("**VFI.OP i VFI.OL – łącznie dla NTG+HTG**")) %>%
tab_style(style = cell_text(weight = "bold"), locations =
cells_row_groups()) %>%
opt_row_stripping() %>%
tab_options(table.font.size = px(14))

```

Table 4: VFI.OP i VFI.OL – łącznie dla NTG+HTG

	Mean	SD	Median	Min	Max	N
VFI.OL						
NTG+HTG	90.76	7.48	92.00	74.00	99.00	25
VFI.OP						
NTG+HTG	91.04	6.56	92.00	76.00	98.00	25

VFI OP

Shapiro-Wilk test for VFI OP(grupa 'HTG')

- Statystyka W = 0.807
- p-value = 0.01783

Shapiro-Wilk test for VFI OP(grupa 'NTG')

- Statystyka W = 0.916
- p-value = 0.1684

```

dane_noK <- dane %>%
  filter(group %in% c("NTG", "HTG")) %>%
  mutate(
    group = factor(group, levels = c("NTG", "HTG")),
    `VFI.OP` = as.numeric(gsub(",", ".", as.character(`VFI.OP`)))
  )

t_welch <- t.test(`VFI.OP` ~ group, data = dane_noK, var.equal = FALSE)
t_welch

```

Welch Two Sample t-test

```

data: VFI.OP by group
t = -2.725, df = 22.312, p-value = 0.01227
alternative hypothesis: true difference in means between group NTG and group
HTG is not equal to 0
95 percent confidence interval:

```

```
-10.445269 -1.421398
sample estimates:
mean in group NTG mean in group HTG
      88.66667      94.60000
```

VFI OL

Shapiro-Wilk test for VFI OL(grupa 'HTG')

- Statystyka W = 0.908
- p-value = 0.2708

Shapiro-Wilk test for VFI OL(grupa 'NTG')

- Statystyka W = 0.879
- p-value = 0.04552

```
dane_noK <- dane %>%
  filter(group %in% c("NTG","HTG")) %>%
  mutate(
    group = factor(group, levels = c("NTG","HTG")),
    `VFI.OL` = as.numeric(gsub(",",".", as.character(`VFI.OL`)))
  )

t_welch <- t.test(`VFI.OL` ~ group, data = dane_noK, var.equal = FALSE)
t_welch
```

Welch Two Sample t-test

```
data: VFI.OL by group
t = -2.4172, df = 18.909, p-value = 0.02592
alternative hypothesis: true difference in means between group NTG and group
HTG is not equal to 0
95 percent confidence interval:
 -11.0105018 -0.7894982
sample estimates:
mean in group NTG mean in group HTG
      88.4      94.3
```